

FORENSIC ACCOUNTING EDUCATION AMONGST ACCOUNTING GRADUATES IN OMAN: ACADEMICIANS' AND PRACTITIONERS' PERSPECTIVES TO BRIDGE THE GAP

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Abstract

The study investigates the integration of forensic accounting into higher education institutions' (HEIs) accounting curricula in Oman and its alignment with industry requirements. Using a qualitative inductive approach, the research analyzed interview data from academicians and practitioners, alongside curriculum documents. Six themes emerged: curriculum modernization, integration of forensic accounting, teaching methods, local and global perspectives, real-life scenarios, and skills development. Findings highlight that forensic accounting is indirectly addressed within existing modules like auditing and corporate finance, with no standalone courses. Academicians identified significant gaps in the curriculum, including limited coverage of forensic-specific competencies such as fraud detection and investigative techniques. Practitioners emphasized a knowledge-skills gap among graduates, citing deficiencies in practical application, technical proficiency, and familiarity with tools. Training initiatives, while addressing some shortcomings, remain reactive and limited in scope. Key recommendations include introducing dedicated forensic accounting courses, integrating region-specific issues (e.g., VAT fraud, financial manipulations), emphasizing practical training through workshops and internships, and fostering academia-industry collaboration. Regular curriculum updates informed by industry insights and advanced technologies such as artificial intelligence was also suggested to enhance student readiness. The study underscores the importance of bridging theoretical and practical divides in accounting education to meet the growing demand for forensic accounting professionals in Oman and the Gulf region. While offering valuable insights, the research acknowledges its limitations, such as the absence of student and alumni perspectives, and suggests further exploration through quantitative methods and comparative studies across GCC institutions.

Keywords: Forensic Accounting, Curriculum, Training, Oman, Competencies.

INTRODUCTION

Forensic accounting is highly recognized for its critical role in addressing financial irregularities, fraud, and corporate governance for legality and transparency assurance. Forensic accountants need a combination of investigative, analytical, and accounting skills in modern economic systems.

To combat corporate scrutiny and financial crimes, the demand for professionals with forensic accounting expertise is growing globally (Bhasin, 2013; Shbeilat & Alqatamin, 2022; Afriyie et al, 2023). Accounting professionals require specialized knowledge in addition to traditional accounting principles to meet today's complex challenges.

Therefore, integrating forensic accounting (FA) into academic curricula is important for developing desired competencies (Albuquerque & Dos Santos, 2023). There is a high requirement to bridge the gap between theoretical knowledge instructed in educational institutions and the practical skills required by the profession. Accounting graduates need a robust and practice-oriented approach to accounting education to be able to handle the complexities of forensic investigations (Churyk, Ndicu, & Pearson, 2023).

Economic reforms and Vision 2040 of Oman emphasize economic growth through transparency and accountability (Supreme Council for Planning, 2019). Forensic accounting proficiency in fraud detection, investigation, and regulatory compliance is critical for maintaining financial integrity in both the public and private sectors. However, despite the global emphasis on integrating forensic accounting into education, localized challenges such as resource limitations and a lack of comprehensive educational programs may hinder the progress of developing skilled professionals (Horan & Saiedian, 2021).

Under the aspiration of Vision 2040, Oman is persuading sustainable education targets (Bhandari & Mohite, 2024) but none of the studies reports in well-known journals about forensic education in Oman. Prominent studies have discussed forensic accounting in Oman in other aspects. For example, forensic accounting and sustainable corporate governance (Rehman & Hashim, 2019, 2021), and certified accountant career (Bhat & Khan, 2023).

Forensic accounting is one of the means to control, eliminate, and mitigate fraud (Rehman & Hashim, 2018). The capacity of graduates to address complex problems of fraud and regulatory compliance becomes limited due to the absence of a comprehensive curriculum by the higher education Institutions (HEIs).

In the GCC and particularly in Oman, lack of collaboration among education providers, professional bodies, and industry stakeholders affects the ability of graduates to support the country's economic integrity and regulatory framework (Al-Husaini, 2022; Komarev & Preobragenskaya, 2022). Therefore, a structured approach to curriculum enhancement and capacity building will meet the demand for forensic accounting professionals in Oman. This expectation requires accounting programs to address core topics that feature the students' knowledge and skills development to apply in professional practice.

This study aims to provide insights from the selected country and highlight the current state of FA from multiple perspectives. It also highlights the need for an inclusive curriculum in Omani HEIs and engages key stakeholders to explore the relevance and effectiveness of forensic accounting education in Oman.

The study presents the existing state of forensic accounting education in Oman and suggests recommendations to fulfil the needs of the accounting professional market in Oman. Identification of curriculum gaps will ensure that graduates have capability for the requirements of the forensic accounting profession. The findings of this study provide valuable insights for policymakers, educators, and practitioners to improve the employability and effectiveness of accounting professionals against criminal practices.

To achieve these objectives, this study endeavours to seek answers to the following questions.

1. To what extent do Omani educational institutions integrate contemporary accounting skills into their curricula?
2. What are the gaps in the accounting curricula of Omani universities compared to industry demands?
3. What is the nature of the skills gap between accounting qualification programs and industry requirements in Oman?
4. What collaborative frameworks may help universities, colleges, and industry professionals to co-design continuing curricula to enhance accounting education?

LITERATURE REVIEW

The Development of Forensic Accounting

Forensic and accounting holds different definitions. Forensic addresses issues related legal compliance and regulations, while accounting refers to activities that affect financial records.

According to (Botes & Saadeh ,2018), forensic accounting includes a range of activities in fraud detection, litigation support, and financial investigation. According to the Forensic and Litigation Services Committee at the American Institute of Certified Public Accountants (AICPA; 2004), “*forensic accounting requires the implementation of specialized skills in accounting, auditing, finance, quantitative approaches, law, inspection, and scrutinizing skills to gather, examine, and assess evidence, and to find and share results*”.

Accounting forensics combines traditional accounting expertise with investigative techniques to uncover and prevent financial fraud and misconduct. Forensic accounting has become increasingly important as corporate fraud, economic crimes, and financial transactions have become more complex. Forensic accountants are not only the fraud auditors, but forensic accounting also includes topic such as fraud detection, financial crime investigation, financial manipulations, legal aspects of accounting, and the application of investigative techniques. A forensic accountant utilizes auditing skills, investigative skills, and legal knowledge to investigate financial discrepancies (Crumbley, 2009). Forensic accounting professionals primarily supported legal proceedings and criminal investigations, focusing on fraud detection and litigation support. Considering financial fraud's sophistication and pervasive nature, forensic accounting has expanded to include cybercrime, money laundering, and regulatory compliance (Silverstone et al., 2012). Therefore, expansion of globalization, financial markets have become increasingly complex, and digital transactions is the major reason for the increasing demand for forensic accounting professionals.

Global trends in Forensic Accounting

Economic globalization has created new opportunities, increasing the demand for forensic accountants to handle complex financial investigations (Bhasin, 2016). Besides the issues of corporate governance, financial crimes, such as money laundering and embezzlement have

intensified the need for regulatory scrutiny, particularly, in banking, insurance, and real estate industry (Bhasin, 2016; Saed & Aref, 2020; Wronka, 2023).

Globally, technology is reshaping forensic accounting practices by employing artificial intelligence, block chain analytics, and other software to uncover irregularities in financial data. There is high improvement in fraud detection technology, for example, Block chain technology is tracing financial transactions in cryptocurrency-related fraud (Hossain, 2023). The rise of cybercrime such as hacking and digital identity theft has broadened the scope of forensic accounting for digital forensics into their investigations (Holt, Bossler & Seigfried-Spellar, 2022). The importance of forensic accounting has led to an expansion of forensic accounting education. A wide variety of specialized courses are now available at universities worldwide, while professional bodies, like the Association of Certified Fraud Examiners (ACFE), award certifications such as the Certified Fraud Examiner (CFE) and American Board of Forensic Accounting (ABFA). Forensic accountants can enhance their expertise and credibility through these programs (Courtois & Gendron, 2020).

Corporate governance and risk management is becoming important increasingly. The organization recognizes the role of forensic audit in internal audits, compliance, and fraud prevention. In high-risk industries, forensic accounting interventions have reduced financial irregularities significantly (Hassan et al., 2023). In the recent time, there is a standardization of accounting practices due to globalization. Forensic accounting practices also address the ethical challenges such as data privacy concerns, fair disclosure, and conflicts of interest. Professional organizations have developed important guidelines on integrity and objectivity (Hossain, 2023).

Educational programs aligned with industry patterns can provide students with skills and practical exposure through internships and job placement. Forensic accounting is continually evolving in response to global challenges posed by cybercrime, ethical dilemmas, and pursuit of standardization. In academically advanced education, system at universities has successfully integrated foreign forensic accounting into their curricula. Integration of forensic accounting knowledge and skills through accounting education enable graduates to protect corporate world and economies against fraud and anomalies (Ebaid, 2022). In the Gulf region, Saudi Arabian universities are continually integrating forensic accounting in their curriculum (Alzahrane, 2021; Alblowi, 2023).

The Need for Forensic Accounting Education in Oman

In Oman, corporate governance has evolved with a focus on increasing transparency, accountability, and sustainable business practices. According to Shankaraiah (2005), the study emphasizes that there is an impact from outward international standards also including OECD Principles of Corporate Governance as well as inward regional and local regulation set by Oman recognized via Capital Market Authority. They seek to tackle issues relating to financial disclosures, shareholder rights, and corporate boards' roles and responsibilities, among others. Oman has made significant strides in bringing its governance practices into line with international standards. The adoption of governance codes and International Accounting

Standards (IAS), amongst other initiatives (Shankaraiah, 2005), has led to an improvement in corporate reporting and transparency. Yet, certain challenges remain, especially regarding the adequacy and consistency of financial disclosures, which could hinder Oman from attracting global investors (Sanyal & Hisam, 2018). The larger firms benefit from structured governance frameworks, but the SMEs have a long way to go in achieving full-fledged compliance. However, Oman's ongoing efforts reflect its commitment to strengthening corporate governance, aligning with its broader objectives of economic diversification and global competitiveness (Michael, Awad, & Khalaf, 2023). As the financial transactions are getting more complex as well as the mushrooming of corporate fraud, the need arises to nurture forensic accounting education in Omani higher education system. Rehman and Hashim (2019) state that strong corporate governance promises to increase the role of forensic accounting in unearthing anomalies in public companies. Further, stressing how essential education is in providing skills for the ready preparation of the practitioners for today's corporate defects: their research suggests that forensic accounting aids the advancement of sustainable corporate governance, mediated by the effectiveness of internal audits (Rehman & Hashim, 2018).

Al-Husaini (2022) further emphasizes the critical role of stakeholder collaboration in strengthening forensic investigation capabilities and supporting the development of comprehensive forensic accounting education programs in Oman's academic institutions. Such initiatives are important for developing a well-trained workforce capable of addressing the complexities of modern corporate governance. Collectively, under the framework of enhancement of economic diversification and global competitiveness, Oman is working towards improving corporate governance (Michael, Awad, & Khalaf, 2023).

Simultaneously, the increasing complexity of financial transactions and the rise of corporate fraud accentuate the need for forensic accounting education as part of Oman's higher education system. Strong corporate governance is main enabling factor for forensic accounting to ascertain irregularities in public corporations as per Rehman and Hashim (2019). Such education would lead to programs that prepare professionals for modern corporate problems. The research also concludes forensic accounting would support sustainable corporate governance and internal audits (Rehman & Hashim, 2018).

Forensic Accounting Education in Oman

Compared to educational advance countries, the adoption process of forensic accounting is slower in Oman and other GCC (Gulf Cooperation Council) states as a formal part of accounting education. However, financial system modernization and improvement are in these states in progress. There is a growing recognition of the need to equip accounting graduates with specialized forensic skills required in the job market (Komare & Preobragenskaya, 2022). This situation presents an opportunity for Omani HEIs to revise their curricula to align with global best practices in preparing market-compatible professionals. Despite this, forensic accounting is under addressed in many educational institutions in Oman. Most HEIs offering accounting degrees offer traditional accounting with the least or insufficient emphasis on specialized forensic accounting courses (Al-Khadhari & Al-Busaidi, 2021). This challenges the Omani workforce in the accounting profession because lack of necessary skills among

graduates will hinder their effectiveness in job roles. The gap between accounting education in Omani HEIs and industry needs is challenging. To address emerging crimes, the forensic accounting profession has evolved globally (Odeyemi et al, 2024). Another challenge to HEIs in Oman is lack of qualified faculty members with expertise in forensic accounting (Lodhia, 2017). The availability of expert and trained teaching faculty is important for effective teaching of forensic accounting, universities must recruit instructors with specialized knowledge in fraud detection, legal frameworks, and investigative techniques. Therefore, investment in expert hiring, faculty development, and ongoing training to keep pace with the evolving field of forensic accounting is a challenge for HEIs.

Job market trends in forensic accounting

The role of forensic accounting in the job market has expanded significantly in response to global trends in corporate governance, fraud prevention, and regulatory compliance (Zysman & Wilson, 2020). In developed markets, there is a strong demand for forensic accountants across various sectors, including finance, government, and law enforcement. Forensic accountants are increasingly sought after for their ability to detect financial fraud, conduct audits, and provide expert testimony in legal cases (Peele, 2017). In Oman, the rapid development of sectors such as oil and gas, construction, and finance has led to increased investment and the creation of a more complex financial landscape (Al-Khadhari & Al-Busaidi, 2021). With this growth, there has been an increase in financial risks, including fraud, mismanagement, and corruption. The demand for forensic accounting professionals in Oman is expected to rise, making it imperative for educational institutions to provide specialized training to accounting graduates. Additionally, many Omani businesses and government organizations are beginning to recognize the value of forensic accountants in ensuring financial transparency and compliance with international accounting standards (Zysman & Wilson, 2020).

- Innovative teaching methodologies (e.g., case-based learning, simulation exercises, industry partnerships).
- Integration of technology (e.g., use of data analytics and AI tools in forensic accounting).

Challenges in Developing Forensic Accounting Proficiency

- Academic challenges (e.g., lack of specialized faculty, insufficient course offerings).
- Industry challenges (e.g., limited internship opportunities, low awareness of forensic accounting roles).

The Need for Curriculum Reform

Scholars emphasize for curriculum reform in accounting education due to growing importance of forensic accounting in dealing with financial crimes to improve corporate governance (Crumbley, 2018). The inclusion of forensic accounting in the curriculum would ensure that accounting graduates can identify financial fraud, assess risk, and provide expert opinions in legal matters. Graduates with a strong foundation in forensic accounting would be able to utilize specialized knowledge in fraud detection and investigation (Albrecht, 2019).

HEIs can incorporate the forensic accounting topics into existing accounting courses or develop separate courses; this needs a strategic orientation from HEIs. Peele (2017) suggests that courses such as financial fraud investigation, data analytics, and forensic technology can provide students with the skills required to navigate the modern financial system. Furthermore, practical training, including internships and case studies, can help bridge the gap between theoretical knowledge and real-world application.

METHODOLOGY

This study used exploratory research design to explore diverse perspectives within a specific context. This study employed qualitative method followed a phenomenological framework in examining the perspectives accounting faculty members and practitioners regarding the development of forensic accounting skills among accounting graduates in Oman. Qualitative method provides valuable and provides a deeper understanding of experiences and phenomena within a specific context (Fisher & Stenner, 2011; Mayoh & Onwuegbuzie, 2015). This study is under the influence of the interpretivism paradigm to understand the subjective meanings and experiences of individuals in a specific context. It focuses on interpreting the lived experiences rather than quantifying them; therefore, it aligns with qualitative methods.

Therefore, contemplating the case (Palinkas et al., 2015; Kalu, 2019), study used purposive sampling. Researchers considered the context specific characteristics while selecting participants. Researchers selected six academicians teaching accounting courses from five higher education institutions in Sultanate Oman. Their names and institutional affiliation are anonymous due the absence of their consent to disclose. Similarly, five accounting professionals at managerial positions from private organizations (audit, insurance telecom, and manufacturing) participated into survey. To maintain consistency and flexibility, we used semi-structured interviews to collect data. With the consent of participants, interviews were conducted via virtual platforms (Zoom and Microsoft Teams) and face-to face meetings and recordings. Researchers wrote transcripts to identify codes and themes. Participants received questions prior to the interview. Interviews contained following literature review guided concepts.

- For academicians: *"Investigating the relevance of forensic accounting within academic curricula."*
- For practitioners: *"Understanding the key skills and competencies needed to succeed in forensic accounting."*

Based on the objectives of the study, context, and intended outcomes researchers propose five questions each for academicians and practitioners. Researchers discussed questions with three senior academicians for refinement prior to execute the survey. NVivo software assisted with coding and systematic data organization. Data analysis include a thematic analysis through a series of steps: (1) involving familiarization with the transcripts (2) writing transcripts, (3) coding relevant information, (4) grouping codes into themes, (5) triangulation of information, (6) interpreting the findings in the context of existing literature. Finally, the study conducted a

triangulation of findings among data sources to check convergence, divergence, and complementarity of findings. To ensure credibility and reliability, the study shared preliminary findings with participants and established an audit trail maintaining anonymity of responses. Ethical considerations include obtaining informed consent, ensuring participant confidentiality, and gaining approval from relevant HEIs. The study focuses on Oman, potentially, limiting generalizability to other contexts.

Data analysis

Researchers adopted inductive (data-driven) approach (Braun and Clarke, 2014, 2020) to produce codes reflective of the content of the data, free from any pre-conceived theory or conceptual framework. The process contained following steps: 1) data acquaintance; 2) coding; 3) themes generation; 4) reviewing themes; 5) naming themes; and 6) reporting. Interview transcripts were reviewed, noting initial impressions and patterns. Codes were generated for data segments related to research questions. Distinct themes were identified (Table) and integrated into narratives, discussing their relevance (Table) for both from academicians and practitioners. The process enabled researchers to analyse qualitative data and uncover meaningful patterns and insights.

Interview data from Academicians

Questions	Codes	Theme
1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Traditional accounting • Indirect integration • Forensic accounting elements • Exploration • Future incorporation 	Integration
2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use of case studies • Guest lectures by industry professionals. • Assignments/ projects • Ethical dilemmas 	Teaching method
3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Traditional accounting education • Limited coverage of forensic-specific skills • Need for specialized training. 	Curriculum
4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Alignment with international standards • Relevance of fraud prevention • Growing awareness of forensic accounting 	Local and global perspective
5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Examination of actual fraud cases • Auditing study • Regulatory compliance • Ethical decisions 	Real-life scenarios
6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Analysis skills • Critical thinking • Auditing • Risk assessment • Knowledge of regulations • Communication skills • Proficiency in technology 	Forensic accounting skills

Theme	Description
Integration	Integration of forensic accounting into curriculum
Teaching method	Teaching methods and pedagogical approaches
Curriculum	Curriculum relevance to forensic accounting needs.
Local and global perspective	Relevance to local and global forensic accounting needs.
Real-life scenarios	There is a need to apply knowledge and skills to real-life scenarios.
Forensic accounting skills	Competencies and skills required for forensic accounting.

Derived themes and their descriptions indicate that forensic accounting in Omani HEIs includes into the curriculum through related topics, such as auditing and ethics, but not as an explicit course or program of study. In response of an interview question one respondent shared the following information. *“In our college, forensic accounting is not a standalone module. We deal topics of forensic accounting in advanced accounting modules such as Corporate Finance, Auditing, and Taxation. In these modules we have included knowledge content related to fraudulent activities, common issues, and ethical aspects. In summary, I can conclude that the topics of forensic accounting are covered indirectly and partially instead of having forensic accounting as a standalone course”*

The similar responses were from other four respondents who established that institutions do not offer forensic accounting as a separate module rather related components cover its topics.

Higher education institutions in Oman use different teaching approaches to introduce the principles of forensic accounting to create student interest and practical experience despite there not being a specific course of study in this area. For example, a participant said, *“We predominantly work with textbooks, where fraud examination and ethical issues are part of course material. Students analyse and discuss case studies and real-life issues of the companies to understand regulatory issues, violations and criminal acts. We include research-based assignment to cover such topics. Additionally, we have multiple knowledge sharing sessions by guest speaker’s lectures.”*

Regarding the relevance of content, in most of the cases, the curriculum aligns with traditional approaches to accounting study. Deficiencies in forensic accounting preparation and complementary certifications are obvious which is evident from the following response. *“Definitively the program at our institution is not based on around forensic accounting education. However, our program covers understanding and practice of auditing, ethical issues, and risk assessment, which may partially serve for forensic accounting requirements”*

Similarly, in case of curriculum HEIs approach does not support global accounting practices. Curriculum does not address forensic accounting learning and skills building. The consideration of forensic accounting stands on an indirect approach to prepare students for standardized reporting. One of the responses acknowledged this as following. *“The content we offer is relevant to global standards such as International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) and auditing practices. However, possibility of improvement is there to contextualize the course content to address fraud scenarios, regulations, and trends at local level”.*

Data indicates that there is a lack of practical examples to connect theoretical knowledge with real-world forensic accounting scenarios; the following citation from interviews indicates that. *"We select cases of fictitious fraud cases based on actual events. We assign work to students to analyse and evaluate issues. Sometimes, we discuss fraud cases through multimedia to connect our students with practice. We do not have opportunity for skills buildings with on hand training experience."*

There is significant gap in skill building necessary for accounting graduates to succeed in forensic accounting. We noted that in skills building, HEIs depend upon supplementary learning through case studies. Faculty at HEIs is fully cognizant of the importance of generic skills. One of the respondents reflected this gap as following. *"Analytical skills and decision-making proficiency is very important for graduates. They must be detail-oriented and be well grounded in professional mind-set. Furthermore, should be proficient in use of data analysis tools. Graduates must have knowledge of legal frameworks and communication skills to present investigations in a clearly and professionally manner."*

Interview Data from Accounting Practitioners

Question	Codes	Theme
1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Readiness • Technical skills • Awareness of legal framework 	Knowledge and skills gap
2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Familiarizing • On boarding • Communication • Presentation Skills 	Training initiatives
3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Procurement fraud • Fraud trends • VAT fraud 	Trends and Regional issues
4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Anti-money laundering laws • Fraud detection 	Academia-industry Collaboration
5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Curriculum updates • Experiential Learning • Knowledge Sharing 	Modernization of curriculum

Theme	Description
Knowledge and skills gap	Graduates have good academic knowledge but lack the ability to apply it in practical forensic accounting work.
Training initiatives	Organizations provide basic training such as on boarding to fill the skill gaps among graduates, including forensic tools, case mock-ups, ethical awareness workshops, and communication skills. Training is continually on selected topics.
Trends and Regional issues	Seminars on region-specific issues in Oman and the Gulf on VAT fraud, procurement fraud, financial manipulations, and ESG reporting violations will enhance the scope of learning forensic accounting.
Academia-industry Collaboration	Workshops and lectures by practitioners and actual case will further enhance students' readiness for professional challenges.
Modernization of curriculum	Collaboration between academics at institutions and practitioners might help students to become proficient in forensic accounting.

The interview data revealed key themes highlighting both shortcomings and potential in forensic accounting education. Themes (Table) form a road map for enhancing forensic accounting programs, notably in Oman and the Gulf area.

Knowledge and skills gap

Graduates from accounting programs often possess theoretical knowledge but lack the practical skills required to apply their learning in real-world contexts. Identifying this gap, one of the interviewees noted that graduates lack familiarity with forensic tools, techniques, fraud laws, and court procedures. A respondent said, *"Generally, graduates come with a satisfactory knowledge and grasp of foundational accounting principles, but they often lack specialized knowledge and skill in forensic accounting. Particularly, they lack skills in fraud detection, data analytics, and comprehending legal implications."* Indication of this discrepancy underlines the necessity of practical exposure during academic programs; prepare students ready to encounter the challenges in forensic accounting.

Training initiatives

Regarding training initiatives, respondents explained that organizations recognize this gap and provide essential training for new hires, which is not sufficient for their readiness. These activities include on boarding training for forensic technologies, case simulations, ethical awareness workshops, and communication skills. One quote from interviews explains, *"We provide on-the-job training to newly hired accounting staff. The focus of the training is on using techniques of fraud examination, data analysis, and case management. The mode of training is workshops on forensic tools like ACL and IDEA. Training also has sessions on interpreting financial evidence in legal contexts."* A second observation was, *"Our on boarding programs bridge the academic gap by training on use of tools and techniques. We often use case mock-ups."* This indicates that the training programs integrate technical skills, legal understanding, and problem-solving and emphasize practical, hands-on experience and to prepare accounting staff for their roles effectively. However, we may conclude that training is reactive and restricted to limited topics, it does not provide thorough and ongoing learning, instead.

Trends and Regional Issues

Interview responses highlighted the issues of training needs. To remain relevant, training in forensic accounting must address region-specific issues. Current topics such as VAT fraud, irregularities in procurement, financial misrepresentation, and violations in ESG (Environmental, Social, and Governance) reporting are emerging issues in the field of forensic accounting. One respondent observed, *"We have seminars focusing on regional challenges, like VAT fraud, procurement irregularities presenting the unique concerns of Oman and GCC."* Another respondent quotes, *"Knowledge of anti-money laundering regulations, digital fraud detection, and compliance with local financial laws is important for practitioners who join the job newly. Additionally, graduates must have an update information on emerging tool like block chain's role in forensic accounting and use of AI in fraud detection."* The concern of accounting professionals underscores the importance of a comprehensive training approach combining regional insights, regulatory compliance, and technological aspects to prepare new

practitioners for the effectiveness of their role. Therefore, integration of region-specific challenges into training programs and academic curricula will enhance applicability of forensic accounting education.

Academia-Industry Collaboration

The importance of industrial and academic cooperation is common in the interviews. For better preparation of students, practical experience gained through internships, case studies, and practitioner-led courses is essential. For, example one of the interviewees underlined, *"Collaboration between universities and industry can be highly beneficial. For example, practitioners can support through guest lectures, internship can provide hands-on experience. This combination and joint effort will bridge the gap between theoretical knowledge and practical application."* We can establish this point that such collaborations can bridge the gap between theoretical learning and practical application; equip students with the skills and confidence to work in their professional roles.

Modernization of Curriculum

The modernization of academic curricula emerged as a critical need through the interviews. Participants frequently cited for the collaboration between academic institutions and forensic accounting practitioners to make the accounting study content relevant and practical. One of the respondents suggested, *"There is a need of updates in the curriculum on regular basis. If guided by professional's insights, this can enhance the capabilities of graduates who are intend to join forensic accounting profession."* The arguments emphasize for regular curriculum updates. Therefore, industry informed curriculum can ensure learning of theoretical principles with adoption of the latest tools and techniques of forensic investigations.

Triangulation and Integration of Findings

Data	Source	Findings
Interview Data (academicians)	Semi-structured interviews with teaching faculty	Data analysis reveals that Oman's HEIs do not integrate adequate forensic accounting into accounting curricula, students are with limited knowledge of fraud detection, investigation techniques, and ethics. This indicates the necessity to bridge the gap between theoretical education and practical skills to meet the growing demand for forensic accounting profession. Enhancing curriculum relevance with updated content and teaching methods is essential, as academicians recognize the importance of developing key competencies among graduates.
Interview data (practitioners)		Regarding skills, key deficiencies such as limited familiarity with forensic tools, fraud detection techniques, and legal frameworks were reported. Practitioners reported some training initiatives from organizations, but this is a kind of reflective training not a comprehensive. Findings indicate deficiency of familiarity with trends. Findings emphasize on industry and academia collaboration and recommend regular updates in the curriculum. In summary, addressing the skills gap requires a multifaceted approach combining academic and industry collaboration, curriculum, and training. Findings recommend a targeted training of tools and

		technologies in context of region-specific challenges for the forensic accounting profession.
Documents Analysis	Curriculum, Syllabus documents (corporate finance, auditing, taxation)	The analysis of the curriculum and program documents (i.e., study plans and syllabus) for accounting degree programs revealed a lack of emphasis on forensic accounting requirements. None of the selected HEIs offers forensic accounting as a separate course. Curricula focus on theoretical concepts and problem solving. Programs are evident to have a focus on core areas such as financial accounting, corporate finance, auditing, and taxation. However, these are important but do not address specialist forensic accounting requirements such as fraud detection, investigative procedures, and legal frameworks. Forensic accounting topics either are absent or partially addressed in syllabus, limiting students' exposure to this essential field. This limits student's ability to satisfy the growing demand for forensic accountants in Oman. The syllabus also indicates significant gaps: corporate finance lacks content on financial irregularities, auditing overlooks fraud detection approaches and advanced tools, and taxes does not address fraud detection or region-specific issues such as VAT fraud.

Triangulation of data revealed following insights.

Convergence: Data sets emphasize on the strategic need for integrating forensic accounting and competency development. Both the data sources agree on the inadequacy of forensic accounting coverage in HEI curriculum. Both sources indicate that the training programs may enhance practical skills and adaptability, but the academic programs lack practical and industry-specific applications.

Divergence: Academicians speak about the limited integration of forensic accounting in accounting curriculum. The document analysis provided substantial evidence of curriculum gaps and topic specific content deficiencies. Therefore, bridging this divergence by incorporating strategic insight as comprehensive curriculum reforms will address the issue effectively.

Complementarity: The analysis of documents provides evidence of the theoretical focus in the curriculum, which supports the need for enhancement of program content. Interview data sources provided a shared recognition of gaps in forensic accounting education. Their ideas align in identifying significant gaps in the integration of forensic accounting within accounting programs in Oman's HEIs. Insights from interviews of both the groups indicated a complementarity in issues need improvement like ethical cognizance, skills for fraud detection, and real-world application, it aligns with the document analysis which reveals gaps in relevant course content. This shared perspective reinforces the argument for integrating forensic accounting into the curriculum to better equip graduates for the workforce.

DISCUSSION

The outcomes highlight significant knowledge and competency gaps in forensic accounting education, necessitate for curriculum updates to meet industry demands. Graduates often lack practical skills and hands-on training in essential tools, techniques, and the legal aspects of

financial investigations, limiting limits their ability to detect and address fraud effectively. A disconnect between theoretical education and practical application leaves many graduates inexperienced in auditing and unaware of necessary frameworks.

Practitioners emphasize the importance of on boarding programs and focused training to bridge these gaps. Introducing fresh graduates to forensic tools, ethical principles, and effective communication strategies through workshops, simulations, and case study-based learning can facilitate the transition from theory to practice. Tailored seminars addressing region-specific challenges, such as VAT fraud, financial irregularities in reporting, and procurement fraud, are particularly crucial. Enhancing collaboration between industry and academia can further align educational content with professional requirements.

Academics recognize the need for integrating forensic accounting into accounting and business programs at higher education institutions (HEIs) in Oman. Current curricula provide limited exposure to fraud detection, investigation techniques, and ethical considerations, creating a gap in meeting the local and global demand for forensic accounting professionals. The curriculum must incorporate up-to-date content and methodologies, focusing on local and global trends, to develop graduates with competencies in detail orientation, proactive analysis, communication skills, and technological proficiency.

Both practitioners and academics advocate for curriculum modernization, effective training programs, and industry collaboration to cultivate a workforce equipped to address the evolving challenges in forensic accounting. These initiatives are essential to preparing graduates for the dynamic demands of Oman and the Gulf region, ultimately contributing to improved fraud prevention and investigation capabilities across sectors.

Triangulation of interviews, surveys, and document analysis reveals that accounting courses impart significant knowledge of accounting theory and traditional practice. The alignment across multiple data sources provides a comprehensive and well-substantiated understanding of the issue with converging and complimentary insights. Complementary insights balanced divergence regarding integration of forensic accounting in accounting curriculum. In summary, incorporation of regulatory framework related content, formal training, and field related case studies would amplify the program.

Recommendations

- 1) Introduce distinguished forensic accounting courses in the accounting degree programs to address region-specific issues such as VAT fraud, procurement fraud, and financial irregularities to prepare the graduates against local and regional job market challenges.
- 2) Practical training components such as case studies, workshops, etc., to offer will enhance the potential of graduates.
- 3) Collaboration between higher education institutions on partnerships with industries to offer internships to enhance the employability of graduates.
- 4) Include data analytics and artificial intelligence as a part of practical training.

- 5) Conduct guest lectures, seminars, and mentorship programs with forensic accounting professionals to expose students to the realities of challenges and solutions in the field.
- 6) A systematic review of the academic programs integrated into the institutional framework will ensure the curriculum remains relevant to address the emerging needs of accounting careers.
- 7) Course upgrading of teachers/faculty is compulsory to enhance their competency for effective instruction of current knowledge and skills.

LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH

Study potentially overlooks the perspectives of student's alumni which is very important in understanding the effectiveness of current curricula. The study used qualitative data and document analysis. Quantitative data can provide statistical robustness to outcomes. Interview data may have some biases due to subjective opinions, or sometime institutional priorities. Moreover, document data is static in nature. Another unexplored issue is the capacity of HEIs in designing and delivering forensic accounting related materials and learning activities. Therefore, generalization of these results out of Oman is restricted because of the above limitations.

Limitations provide opportunities for further exploration in addressing the gaps identified in the study. Future research can incorporate a broader range of stakeholders such as students, alumni, and broader range industry satisfaction. Assessment of capabilities of institutions offering accounting degree will enhance the understanding of gaps in updating accounting education with reference to emerging industry trends. Future studies can expand the scope of this topic by conducting comparative research between HEIs with institutions in other GCC.

References

- 1) Afriyie, S. O., Akomeah, M. O., Amoakohene, G., Ampimah, B. C., Ocloo, C. E., & Kyei, M. O. (2023). Forensic accounting: A novel paradigm and relevant knowledge in fraud detection and prevention. *International Journal of Public Administration*, 46(9), 615-624.
- 2) Agarwal, N. A. N. D. I. N. I. (2024). Legal Aspects of Corporate Fraud in White Collar Crimes in India. *Indian Journal of Legal Review*, 4(2), 728-739.
- 3) Alblowi, K. (2023). A Three-Tiered Analysis of the Factors Influencing the Adoption of Forensic Accounting Field in Saudi Arabia. *International Journal of Professional Business Review*, 8(6), e02185-e02185.
- 4) Albuquerque, F., & Dos Santos, P. G. (2023). Recent Trends in Accounting and Information System Research: A Literature Review Using Textual Analysis Tools. *FinTech*, 2(2), 248-274.
- 5) Al-Husaini, Y. S. S. (2022). *Enhancing cloud forensic investigation relationships between law enforcement and local cloud service providers: Oman as a case study* (Doctoral dissertation, Ph. D. thesis, School Accounting, Inf. Syst. Supply Chain, College Bus. Law, RMIT Univ., Melbourne, VIC, Australia).
- 6) Alzahrane, M. (2021). *Forensic Accounting Education, Practice, and Career Path in Saudi Arabia* (Doctoral dissertation, University of South Florida).
- 7) American Institute of Certified Public Accountants. (2019, July 10). *AICPA issues new professional standards for forensic accounting service providers*. Retrieved from <https://www.aicpa.org>

- 8) Bhandari, V., & Mohite, V. (2024). Role of higher education institutions in developing digital competence in Sultanate of Oman: a step towards achieving Vision 2040. *Library Hi Tech*.
- 9) Bhasin, M. L. (2013). Corporate governance and forensic accountants' role: Global regulatory action scenario. *International Journal of Accounting Research*, 42(826), 1-19.
- 10) Bhasin, M. L. (2016). Survey of creative accounting practices: an empirical study. *Wulfenia Journal*, 23(1), 143-162.
- 11) Bhat, M. A., & Khan, S. T. (2023). Determinants of accounting students' decision to pursue career as ACCA-certified accountants: a case study of Omani students. *Management & Sustainability: An Arab Review*, 2(3), 217-238.
- 12) Botes, V. and Saadeh, A. (2018), "Exploring evidence to develop a nomenclature for forensic accounting", *Pacific Accounting Review*, Vol. 30 No. 2, pp. 135-154. <https://doi.org/10.1108/PAR-12-2016-0117>
- 13) Churyk, N. T., Ndicu, M., & Pearson, T. C. (2023). Fostering Professional Research Skills in the Undergraduate Accounting Curriculum. In *Advances in Accounting Education: Teaching and Curriculum Innovations* (pp. 29-57). Emerald Publishing Limited.
- 14) Courtois, C., & Gendron, Y. (2020). The show must go on! Legitimization processes surrounding certified fraud examiners' claim to expertise. *European Accounting Review*, 29(3), 437-465.
- 15) Crumbley, D. L. (2009). So what is forensic accounting? *The ABO Reporter*, 9.
- 16) Ebaid, I. E. S. (2022). An exploration of accounting students' attitudes toward integrating forensic accounting in accounting education. *International Journal of Law and Management*, 64(4), 337-357.
- 17) Fisher Jr, W. P., & Stenner, A. J. (2011). Integrating qualitative and quantitative research approaches via the phenomenological method. *International Journal of Multiple Research Approaches*, 5(1), 89-103.
- 18) Hassan, S. W. U., Kiran, S., Gul, S., Khatatbeh, I. N., & Zainab, B. (2023). The perception of accountants/auditors on the role of corporate governance and information technology in fraud detection and prevention. *Journal of Financial Reporting and Accounting*.
- 19) Holt, T. J., Bossler, A. M., & Seigfried-Spellar, K. C. (2022). *Cybercrime and digital forensics: An introduction*. Routledge.
- 20) Horan, C., & Saiedian, H. (2021). Cybercrime investigation: Landscape, challenges, and future research directions. *Journal of Cybersecurity and Privacy*, 1(4), 580-596.
- 21) Hossain, M. Z. (2023). Emerging Trends in Forensic Accounting: Data Analytics, Cyber Forensic Accounting, Cryptocurrencies, and Blockchain Technology for Fraud Investigation and Prevention. *Cyber Forensic Accounting, Cryptocurrencies, and Blockchain Technology for Fraud Investigation and Prevention* (May 16, 2023).
- 22) Hossain, M. Z. (2023). Emerging Trends in Forensic Accounting: Data Analytics, Cyber Forensic Accounting, Cryptocurrencies, and Blockchain Technology for Fraud Investigation and Prevention. *Cyber Forensic Accounting, Cryptocurrencies, and Blockchain Technology for Fraud Investigation and Prevention* (May 16, 2023).
- 23) Kalu, M. E. (2019). Using emphasis-purposeful sampling-phenomenon of interest-context (EPPiC) framework to reflect on two qualitative research designs and questions: A reflective process. *The Qualitative Report*, 24(10), 2524-2535.
- 24) Knechel, W. R. (2022). Auditing: Principles and practice in a digital world. *Accounting Horizons*, 36(2), 1-25.

- 25) Komarev, I., & Preobragenskaya, G. (2022). A framework of market-relevant accounting competencies for the Gulf Cooperation countries (GCC). *Journal of Accounting Education*, 59, 100782.
- 26) Mayoh, J., & Onwuegbuzie, A. J. (2015). Toward a conceptualization of mixed methods phenomenological research. *Journal of mixed methods research*, 9(1), 91-107. Michael, J., Awad, A. B., & Khalaf, B. A. (2023). Exploring environmental, social, and governance and bank performance in the Gulf Cooperation Council region [Special issue]. *Corporate Law & Governance Review*, 5(2), 192–200. <https://doi.org/10.22495/clgrv5i2sip6>
- 28) Palinkas, L. A., Horwitz, S. M., Green, C. A., Wisdom, J. P., Duan, N., & Hoagwood, K. (2015). Purposeful sampling for qualitative data collection and analysis in mixed method implementation research. *Administration and policy in mental health and mental health services research*, 42, 533-544.
- 29) Rehman, A. and Hashim, F. (2018), “Literature review: preventive role of forensic accounting and corporate governance maturity”, *Journal of Governance and Integrity (JGI)*, Vol. 1 No. 2, pp. 68-93.
- 30) Rehman, A., & Hashim, F. (2018, January). Forensic accounting on corporate governance maturity mediated by internal audit: A conceptual overview. In 1st Economics and Business International Conference 2017 (EBIC 2017) (pp. 161-168). Atlantis Press.
- 31) Rehman, A., & Hashim, F. (2019). Impact of mature corporate governance on detective role of forensic accounting: case of public listed companies in Oman. *KnE Social Sciences*, 637-665.
- 32) Rehman, A., & Hashim, F. (2019). Impact of mature corporate governance on detective role of forensic accounting: case of public listed companies in Oman. *KnE Social Sciences*, 637-665.
- 33) Rehman, A., & Hashim, F. (2021). Can forensic accounting impact sustainable corporate governance? *Corporate Governance: The International Journal of Business in Society*, 21(1), 212-227.
- 34) Rehman, A., & Hashim, F. (2021). Can forensic accounting impact sustainable corporate governance? *Corporate Governance: The International Journal of Business in Society*, 21(1), 212-227.
- 35) Saed, H. A., & Aref, H. S. (2020). Criminal Responsibility for The Crime of Administrative, Financial Corruption and the Crime of Money Laundering. *Academic Journal of Nawroz University*, 9(2), 291-309.
- 36) Sanyal, S., & Hisam, M. W. (2018). Corporate governance in emerging economies: A study of the Sultanate of Oman. *International Journal of Business and Administration Research Review*, 3(20), 27–29. Retrieved from <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/323771858>
- 37) Shankaraiah, K., & Rao, D. N. (2005). Corporate governance and accounting standards in Oman. *Research in Accounting Regulation*, 18, 291–292. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1052-0457\(05\)18016-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1052-0457(05)18016-3)
- 38) Shbeilat, M. K., & Alqatamin, R. M. (2022). Challenges and forward-looking roles of forensic accounting in combating money laundering: Evidence from the developing market. *Journal of Governance and Regulation/Volume*, 11(3).
- 39) Silverstone, H., Sheetz, M., Pedneault, S., & Rudewicz, F. (2012). *Forensic accounting and fraud investigation for non-experts*. John Wiley & Sons.
- 40) Vision, O. (2019). 2040. *Supreme Council for Planning, Muscat, Sultanate of Oman*. See: <https://www.scp.gov.om/en/Projects.aspx>.
- 41) Wronka, C. (2023). Financial crime in the decentralized finance ecosystem: new challenges for compliance. *Journal of Financial Crime*, 30(1), 97-113.